

Introduction

to the

Framework

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THE FRAMEWORK AND ITS ACCOMPANYING DOCUMENTS: HANDBOOK AND WORKBOOK

The TransACTION! Framework describes 5 steps to make qualitative educational multimedia. This document gives you a quick introduction into the framework and adds some context on how to use it. To empower you in integrating this model into your daily practice, we have created two additional resources, referred to as the “handbook” and the “workbook”.

The handbook provides you with tangible scenarios and insights that can assist you in the multimedia production process. Meanwhile, the workbook serves as a comprehensive record of your multimedia project’s progress, capturing considerations at each step. It functions as a log, replacing the need for detailed meeting reports.

Together, the handbook and the workbook guide you through the different stages of multimedia production in higher education. We believe that it is beneficial to repeat this cycle for every single multimedia product you produce, but it is up to you to decide how thoroughly you follow these guidelines. Perhaps you will closely follow this handbook and workbook for the production of your first multimedia product, and for subsequent recordings, only focus on the scenarios and questions that are most relevant to you. Or maybe you are interested in the further reading chapters of the handbook, but you design your own scenarios for meetings.

HOW TO GET STARTED?

1. Plan your project, 5 dates, one for every step and determine which expertise is needed for every step.
2. For each meeting:
 - a. Determine your work method using the scenarios in the handbook.
 - b. Use the workbook to decide what needs to be discussed and to make a report afterwards.

In an ideal scenario, the implementation of the framework, handbook, and workbook could follow this approach:

When it becomes evident that educational multimedia needs to be developed for a course, a series of five project meetings can be scheduled, with one dedicated to each step outlined in the framework. The topic and focus for each meeting can be found within this document.

At the project's outset, the designated project leader can extend invitations to the relevant stakeholders for participation in each distinct phase or meeting. It is advisable to allocate approximately two hours per meeting. Take into account some preparation before meetings might be necessary, depending on how you want to achieve the outcome. Especially the last step will bring extra workload once tasks are divided. If it turns out that multiple media products (videos, podcasts, video quizzes, ...) need to be made, for each product the same 5 meetings need to be scheduled. When managing multiple parallel projects, it's worth noting that step 1 will demand less time since you'll find that the same course-related considerations come up repeatedly.

In the workbook, the person in charge can see what needs to be discussed and which decisions need to be made for each step. During or after each meeting, the corresponding questions for each step can be filled in like a logbook. This way, all stakeholders can track the project's progress. The workbook can even be used as a tool to approve and validate previously made decisions.

The handbook provides suggestions for the working method to be used during the meetings, to obtain answers to the questions in the workbook. Additionally, in the handbook, you can find extra topics and themes for each step that you can review, if desired, to prepare for each meeting.

CO-CREATION

An important principle of the “TransACTION!” project is the search for a way to facilitate (more) co-creation. In the handbook, you will find advice on how to involve your stakeholders in each step.

When you think of “co-creation”, you may first think of direct colleagues, but other stakeholders could also provide added value in the production process of educational multimedia. Think, for example, of services and staff (“3rd space”) with didactic, technical, or multimedia expertise. Or students who have completed or have yet to complete the course in which the educational multimedia will serve as learning material. Finally, there may also be other students who may not be directly involved in the course but can provide valuable insights for other reasons. The scenarios and insights were developed with all these potential stakeholders in mind.

The term “co-creation” can be interpreted in a strict sense or in a milder sense, which allows for varying degrees of participation. Interpreting co-creation in the strict sense of the word means that all parties involved have equal say and ownership over the process and final outcome. This approach requires a high level of collaboration and communication between all parties, as well as a willingness to compromise and integrate different perspectives.

On the other hand, choosing a milder version of co-creation allows for varying degrees of participation and ownership among the parties involved. In this sense, co-creation may involve consultation or feedback from stakeholders, rather than full participation in the decision-making process.

The degree to which you want to make this process co-creative is up to you. You can go through each step together with a group of stakeholders, consult them as a steering committee after each phase, or involve stakeholders selectively in the phase where they seem most meaningful to you. It is up to you to shape the (co-creative) production process according to your needs, and that starts with the question of who you want to consult when.

STEP 1: Contextualizing

Intermediate product	Context (curriculum, learning goals, content, assessment) and knowing why you will be creating multimedia.
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Where does the multimedia you want to create fit in? What role will it play within the larger context? Consider the following aspects:

- Keep the structure of the course in mind.
 - How does this course fit into the curriculum? Who is the target audience?
 - Determine the learning goals you want the students to reach when completing the course. What do students have to know and be able to do?
 - Gather the content you want to include. Which topics will be part of the course? How are these topics connected? What is a logical division of topics into chapters?
 - Know how you will evaluate the students. How will you assess if they have reached the learning goals?
 - Be aware of the lesson context: will there be physical and/or online classes (synchronous)? Will there be an online course (asynchronous)?
- For which “learning activities” do you want to use multimedia?
 - A learning activity is an activity the student does in order to learn (e.g. watch a video, fill in an exercise, discuss with peers).
 - Start from a blueprint of the course structure. Know how you will cover the content. Always think about what the student will be doing in each section (student perspective).
 - Determine which learning activities you will support with multimedia. Think about the added value multimedia can bring (e.g. clarifying content, illustrate concepts etc.). Take this input to step 2.

STEP 2: Collect & compare

Intermediate product | Collection of existing multimedia materials you can use (directly/with modifications/as inspiration)

Explore how your idea compares to existing materials and how you can use those to improve your own product.

- Does the material you need already exist? E.g. you have made this multimedia yourself before, a colleague has multimedia you can use immediately, you find suitable multimedia in an Open Education Resources database, etc.
- Is there material you can adapt? Similar to the previous point, with an additional step of adapting the material to meet the needs of your context.
- Is there any material you can use as inspiration or as an example, in terms of format or content?

In case of existing material (to use directly or with modifications): always check the copyright regulations that apply and make sure that you have the rights to use (and possibly adapt) this material. More information on copyright and CC licenses can be found in the TransACTION! Open Online Course (module 2, lesson 3).

In case of existing material that you are allowed to use directly: if you choose this option, the process ends here as you will not create new material yourself.

In all other cases, proceed to step 3.

STEP 3: Resources & quality

Intermediate product | List of available resources and goals regarding the final product.

Describe as precisely as possible which goals or expectations the final multimedia product will have to meet and which resources are available to reach this. Take the following considerations into account:

- Process:
 - How much time can you spend?
 - When should the product be finished?
 - How much money can you spend?
 - Can you make use of (external) support?
 - What facilities or set-ups are available?
- People:
 - Who can or should be involved in the process?
 - How should you involve others and communicate with them?
 - Who will evaluate the final product and when?
- Product:
 - What (learning) content will be addressed?
 - What (learning) goal does the multimedia product serve?
 - What are the didactic criteria?
 - What are the technical criteria?
 - What multimedia principles should the product comply with?
 - Are there any expectations in terms of look and feel?

STEP 4: Design

Intermediate product	Decision on type of multimedia, premise, narrative structure and script
If you haven't decided on a type of multimedia product yet, this is the time to do so. This choice will strongly influence the following steps. When deciding which multimedia best suits your concept, these three questions are crucial:	
1. What is the purpose of your multimedia product?	
2. Which method or technique do you want to use to achieve your goal?	
3. What multimedia content type is best suited for this goal?	

In this creative phase, you work on the structure that forms the outline of the multimedia product and then write a concrete script. This is an iterative process of active searching.

This step consists of three parts:

- **Step 4a: Choosing the right type of multimedia**

In this step, you need to select the multimedia elements that will best enhance your content. Consider the purpose of the multimedia: are you aiming to inform, entertain, persuade, or educate your audience? Think about your target audience and their preferences and expectations regarding multimedia. Then choose the method or technique that is most suitable. Determine the type of content you are creating, whether it is a demonstration video, animation, infographic or podcast. Throughout this process, consider the resources you have available, such as your budget, time, and technical skills.

- **Step 4b: Premise and narrative structure**

This step involves outlining the core message and structure of your content. Describe what you want to convey in one concise sentence. This will help you stay focused and ensure that your content has a clear and coherent message. Then generate first ideas on characters, story elements and settings. Think about key moments and a narrative form.

- **Step 4c: Writing the final script**

Now it's time to draft the final script. Start with an introduction that captures the audience's attention and introduces the main topic. In the body, present your key points in a logical and engaging manner, using multimedia elements to support and enhance your message. Conclude by summarizing the main points and providing a clear call to action or closing thought.

STEP 5: Development

Intermediate product	Final multimedia product
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- Production: this is very dependent on the format chosen.
- Post-production: create a first rough draft, then finetune.
- Distribution: coming full circle, you transfer the multimedia product to its suited context.